

CHALLENGES IN TRANSLATING POEMS FROM ONE LANGUAGE TO ANOTHER

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***Absrtact.** The article discusses the obstacles and problems associated with translating poetry from one language to another. Language problems are brought to light, including the difficulty of translating some words literally, variations in word choice, and metaphor interpretation.*

***Key words:** poetry, literally, acceprable, rhyme, tonality, metaphor.*

***Abstrakt.** Maqolada she'ri ni bir tildan ikkinchi tilga tarjima qilish bilan bog'liq to'siqlar va muammolari muhokama qilinadi. Til muammolari, jumladan, ba'zi so'zlarni so'zma-so'z tarjima qilish qiyinligi, so'z tanlashdagi o'zgarishlar va metafora talqini ochiladi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** she'riyat, adabiy, maqbul, qofiya, ohang, metafora.*

***Абстракт.** В статье рассматриваются препятствия и проблемы, связанные с переводом поэзии с одного языка на другой. Выявляются языковые проблемы, в том числе трудности буквального перевода некоторых слов, различия в выборе слов и интерпретации метафор.*

***Ключевые слова:** поэзия, буквальное, приемлемое, рифма, тональность, метафора.*

Poems and other works of literature are generally hard to translate. This is accurate in terms of how challenging it is to translate various forms of materials. In particular, poetry are more difficult to translate for a variety of reasons. There are other things to take into account, such as word selections, metaphorical imagery, and the usage of literal language. The poet's feelings and ideas must also be conveyed by the translation at the same time.

Poems include certain qualities like rhymes, meters, rhythm, and idioms that are not present in other literary works, which makes interpreting them even more challenging. Even most terms are rarely used in casual talks. Thus, this presents an even greater obstacle for those who dare to interpret poetry. A thorough comprehension of grammar and culture is necessary for translation. Both the

conventions of the target language and its speakers' customs must be understood by translators. Furthermore, uncertainty and annoyance are common emotions, even for those who are most seasoned specialists.

There can be several reasons for challenges in translating.

Issues with language. There may be some confusion regarding the proper terminology to employ when translating specific words from one language to another. Certain words cannot always be translated literally into another language. In specific languages, a single English word can have the same meaning as up to three phrases in another language. Or perhaps it's a different technique way. In an English poem, a whole stanza could consist of only one word in another language. The other components of a poem may be destroyed in addition to making translation difficult due to word choice variations. According to Snell-Hornby (1988–1995), "the interpretation of metaphor needs to rely on both the structure and the function of the specific phrase in the context involved, and is unable to be defined by a set of abstraction standards".

Interpretation: literal opposed to figurative. Poems have more profound meanings. There are several words utilized, but they are only metaphors or symbols. The poem as a whole is beautifully composed because of the underlying idea behind those lines. Translators are thus faced with the difficult decision of whether to translate the verse literally, which would make everything sound awkward, or to translate the verses' figurative meaning, which would restrict readers' ability to read the verses critically. According to Peter Newmark (1988), the translator is forced to provide cultural factors equivalents in the intended language in the aforementioned scenario. He recommends that the translator should allow the reader to discover and comprehend the meaning of a particular word for people in different parts of the world.

Cultural and social challenges. A poem may contain certain words that sound unacceptable when translated into another language. The language might also be extremely unsuitable or objectionable. Even though the word used is perfectly appropriate in the language of origin, they could be viewed as impolite. As a result, the translator must now decide which word to use or look for a more vulnerable translation that fits into the culture of the source text.

Sound problem. Poetry is made even more lovely and captivating by this additional component. Readers find themselves engrossed in the poem because of its appealing sounds and rhymes. Unfortunately, it's possible that no word in any other language could preserve these sounds. When made to sound alike, the translated words may have wildly disparate sounds that defy understanding.

To put it briefly, there are many factors to take into account when translating poetry. Poetry translations can take even longer, even though they only contain a few lines or sections. Craig Raine (1994) asserts that translation is the art of the feasible, much like politics, with all the compromises that are inherently involved [par. 1].

Understanding the poet's ideas and the cultural context of the target audience for the translation is also very beneficial. Poems have unique poetic qualities and a distinct literary style, which makes translating them more challenging. Beyond everything else, translating poetry from one language to another is further complicated by the various cultural meanings.

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